

1 **Nanofiltered saponin-rich extract of *Saponaria officinalis* – adsorption and**
2 **aggregation properties of particular fractions**

3 Adam Grzywaczyk^a, Wojciech Smulek^a, Agnieszka Zgoła-Grzeškowiak^b, Ewa Kaczorek^{a*},
4 Anna Zdziennicka^c and Bronisław Jańczuk^c

5

6 *^aInstitute of Chemical Technology and Engineering, Poznań University of Technology,*
7 *Berdychowo 4, 60-965 Poznań, Poland*

8 *^bInstitute of Chemistry and Technical Electrochemistry, Poznań University of Technology,*
9 *Berdychowo 4, 60-965 Poznań, Poland*

10 *^cDepartment of Interfacial Phenomena, Institute of Chemical Sciences, Faculty of Chemistry,*
11 *Maria Curie-Skłodowska University in Lublin, Maria Curie-Skłodowska Sq. 3, 20-031 Lublin,*
12 *Poland*

13

14

15

16

17

18

19 *Corresponding author:

20 e-mail: ewa.kaczorek@put.poznan.pl, tel. +48 (61) 6652601

21 **Abstract**

22 Plant extracts containing saponins combine high emulsifying properties with antibacterial
23 activity, which makes them valuable adjuvants in pharmaceutical and food products. Saponins
24 are natural surfactants present in various plant species, including *Saponaria officinalis*. Due to
25 the variety of chemical structures and diversity of saponins in plant extracts, their surface-active
26 properties are complex and differ from those of chemically pure surfactants. Hence, the aim of
27 the study was to determine the correlation between the composition of *S. officinalis* extracts
28 and their surfactant properties. The first stage of the study was characterization of the
29 composition of the extracts studied by liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry.
30 Then the surface tension of the aqueous solutions of these extracts was measured, which
31 permitted determination of their adsorption and aggregation parameters. The results have
32 pointed out the differences between the properties of the studied extracts and those of pure
33 surfactants of known molecular structure. The constants in the Szyszkowski equation allowed
34 determination of the concentration of the maximum excess of surfactant molecules on the
35 water-air interface and the value of the Gibbs free energy of adsorption. The mentioned
36 parameters and the critical micellization concentration were also determined from the Gibbs
37 adsorption isotherm equation and the Langmuir equation modified by de Boer. The results
38 obtained by these methods were found to be comparable with those determined from the
39 Szyszkowski equation. What is more, it was found that the adsorption parameters correlated
40 with the micelle sizes formed by the components of the tested *S. officinalis* extracts. All these
41 valuable data help devise the informed use of extracts containing saponins in many branches of
42 science and economy.

43 **Key words:** saponin, extract, micelles, nanofiltration, surface activity

45 **1. Introduction**

46 Substances with surface active properties can be found in many different plant species as well
47 as in the animal and even human organisms (Bjerk et al., 2021; Fujimatu et al., 2003; Servillo
48 et al., 2011; Vincken et al., 2007). They play a very important role as components of many
49 different industrial and household products and in a wide range of processes (Benhur et al.,
50 2020; Bjerk et al., 2021; Karlapudi et al., 2018; Rodrigues et al., 2006). Among the surfactants
51 of natural origin, saponins occupy an important position in terms of their practical applications
52 (Tucker et al., 2022). Saponins are used, among others, in the production of food and cosmetics,
53 animal feed and plant protection agents (Hussain et al., 2019; Nizioł-Łukaszewska and Bujak,
54 2018; Tamura et al., 2012). They can be also applied in the environmental protection as
55 additives reacting with the soil pollutants and can be useful for the degradation of synthetic
56 toxic surfactants (Kobayashi et al., 2012). The use of saponins in the medicine and pharmacy
57 is not excluded (Jung et al., 2022; Man et al., 2010). Development of their applications requires
58 a deep knowledge of their physicochemical properties. Among them, the tendency to be
59 adsorbed at the water-air interface and to form micelles in the bulk phase is very important.
60 Unfortunately, it is not easy to determine the tendency of saponins to adsorption at the water-
61 air interface and to form micelles as they are mixtures of various types of chemical compounds,
62 which are the secondary metabolites of plant cells.

63 The composition of saponins depends on their plant origin (Schreiner et al., 2021). An
64 additional difficulty in the analysis of the adsorption and aggregation properties of saponins is
65 determination of their molar mass. For these reasons it is difficult to find unambiguous data
66 about the adsorption and aggregation properties of saponins. If a characterization of the
67 surfactant properties of saponins is given, it is in terms of micellar or emulsifying properties
68 without any deeper analysis or mathematical description of interfacial phenomena (Pradhan et
69 al., 2022; Randriamamonjy et al., 2022). These surfactant properties are most often determined

70 based on the isotherm of the surface tension of their aqueous solutions. For the aqueous
71 solutions of single surfactants or their mixtures, of a known molar mass and molecular
72 dimensions based on the surface tension isotherms, it is easy to determine the concentration of
73 surfactants in the surface monolayer at the water-air interface, orientation of surfactant
74 molecules and the surface area occupied by one molecule in this monolayer as well as the
75 critical micelle concentration (CMC). Thus, it is easy to determine the adsorption and
76 aggregation tendency by solving the known thermodynamic equations. As is commonly known,
77 these equations have been derived on the basis of the activity of the surfactants in the bulk
78 phase. In many cases they are solved against the free Gibbs energy of adsorption and
79 aggregation at the assumption of ideal behaviour of the surfactants and/or their mixtures in
80 aqueous solution. In such case the activity of the surfactants is equal to its mole fraction. To
81 determine the mole fraction of a given compound in the solution its molar concentration or
82 weight in a given volume of solution must be known. Unfortunately, it is more complicated to
83 determine the mole fraction of a given component of the mixture in the case of the aqueous
84 solutions of multicomponent mixtures in which concentrations of single compounds are
85 unknown. The multicomponent mixtures can include not only the surface active compounds. It
86 is possible that to determine, for example, the Gibbs excess concentration in the surface layer
87 of the multicomponent mixtures and/or to analyse of the Szyszkowski equation, the isotherm
88 of the surface tension of aqueous solution of this mixture expressed as a function of the mixture
89 weight in a given volume of the solution can be used. However to determine the tendency to
90 adsorb at the water-air interface and to aggregate in the aqueous solution of the
91 multicomponents mixture the molar fraction or mole concentration of particular component of
92 the mixture should be known or the equations described this tendency should be modified. For
93 this purpose in the previous studies, the properties of a crude extract of saponins from *Saponaria*
94 *officinalis* (Rekiel et al., 2020) were analysed among others, by using the modified Gibbs

95 isotherm equation in which weight was used instead of mole concentration. Thus the aim of the
96 current studies was to determine the total adsorption of saponins and the possibility of their
97 aggregation in the presence of additives based on the thermodynamic relationships modified
98 by us, as well as to evaluate the possibility of using nanofiltration in the saponin purification
99 process. The thermodynamic relationships included the Gibbs isotherm, Szyszkowski and
100 Szyszkowski-Langmuir (often called Frumkin) equations. In these equations instead of the
101 mole concentration, the weight of a given mixture in 1 L was applied. In the case of Gibbs
102 isotherm equation, the usefulness of a mixture weight was proved based on the Gibbs-Duhem
103 equation.

104 Hence, the aim of the study was to explain the correlation between *S. officinalis* extracts
105 composition and their surface activity. In our studies, the extract obtained from *Saponaria*
106 *officinalis* was applied. It was subjected to a process of nanofiltration, as a result of which the
107 E0, E1, E2, E3 and E4 extract fractions various compounds of different molar masses were
108 obtained. Two membranes with the porosity of 500 Da and 3000 Da were used. The middle
109 fraction, E2, should contain the largest amount of saponins (the saponins content was in the
110 range of ~ 2.5kDa- ~ 0.5kDa).

111

112 **2. Materials and methods**

113 **2.1. Materials**

114 Dried and cut roots of *Saponaria officinalis* L. were purchased as a herbal material from Flos,
115 Poland. The methanol (HPLC grade) and other chemicals used in the experiments were from
116 Merck, Germany. The deionized water (18.2 M Ω ·cm) was obtained using Sartorius Stedim
117 (Germany) Mili-Q water purification unit. Millipore[®] membrane filters of cut-off 3.0 kDa and
118 Amicon[®] separation compartment were purchased from Merck Millipore, Germany. Membrane
119 filters of cut-off 0.5 kDa was bought from Starlitech, USA.

120

121 **2.2. Extracts preparation**

122 The process of isolation and separation of different fractions of *S. officinalis* extracts is
123 illustrated in Fig. 1. Firstly, the plant material was placed in a Soxhlet glass extractor (Chempur,
124 Poland) and the extraction process was conducted for 6 h using methanol (10 mL per 1 g of dry
125 roots) as an extractant. Then the solvent was evaporated using a rotary vacuum evaporator
126 (Büchi AG, Switzerland). The obtained dry crude extract (E0 fraction) was dissolved in
127 deionized water (1 g in 100 mL). In the next step, a separation with a 3.0 kDa membrane was
128 performed; the permeate was marked as E1 and the retentate as E4. Then, the E1 fraction was
129 separated using a 0.5 kDa membrane; the permeate was labelled as E3 and the retentate as E2.
130 The term ‘saponins’ can be used to determine both, the plant extract or one specific group of
131 compounds. Throughout this paper, the term saponins is used to describe a plant extract.

132

133 **2.3. Qualitative analysis**

134 The *Saponaria officinalis* L. extract purified on a membrane was analysed by LC-MS/MS. The
135 Ultimate 3000 HPLC system from Dionex (Sunnyvale, CA, USA) coupled with the QTRAP
136 4000 mass spectrometer from AB-Sciex (Foster City, CA, USA) were used. The samples were
137 injected onto a Kinetex Evo C18 column (150 mm × 2.1 mm I.D.; 2.6 µm) from Phenomenex
138 (Torrance, CA, USA). The mobile phase (0.1% formic acid in water and acetonitrile (ACN))
139 was used at a flow rate of 0.3 mL min⁻¹ in the following gradient: 0 min 10% ACN, 5 min 15%
140 ACN, 10 min 20% ACN, 12 min 70% ACN, 15 min 90% ACN, 20 min 90% ACN. The eluate
141 from the column was directed to the ESI source operating in negative ionization mode. The
142 source and mass spectrometer parameters were as follows: source temperature 500°C, nebulizer
143 gas nitrogen at 45 psi, curtain gas nitrogen at 20 psi, declustering potential -50 V, collision gas

144 nitrogen at 10 psi. Mass spectra were recorded in the 300-2500 m/z range. For selected ions,
145 chromatograms and their fragmentations were recorded in the enhanced ion product mode.

146 For the analysis of glycone part of saponins, the GC/MS was used. At first, the derivatization
147 of 50 µg of dehydrated samples with 200 µL of BSTFA (Merck, Germany) was made. The
148 samples were incubated for 1 h at 65°C. After that, hexane was added and the mixture was
149 centrifuged for 5 min to get rid of any solid residue. The liquid phase was collected and then
150 subjected to GC/MS analysis.

151 The GC–MS system used was a Pegasus 4D GCxGC-TOF MS from LECO (Leco Corp., USA).
152 Data acquisition and analysis were performed using standard software supplied by the
153 manufacturer. Substances were separated on a BPX5 capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm ID,
154 0.25 µm film thickness) (Trajan Scientific and Medical, Australia). Temperature program:
155 65°C held for 2 min, 6°C min⁻¹ up to 230°C, held for 5 min, and 6°C min⁻¹ up to 300°C, held for
156 5 min. The temperatures of the injection port and transfer line were set at 280°C and 250°C
157 respectively. Splitless injection mode and helium with a flow rate of 1.00 mL min⁻¹ as carrier
158 gas were used.

159

160 ***2.4. Surface tension***

161 The surface tensions of the deionized water solutions of *S. officinalis* extracts were measured
162 by the du Nuoy platinum ring method using a K20 tensiometer (Krüss, Germany). All of the
163 measurements were conducted at 22 ± 1°C.

164

165 ***2.5. Particle and micelles size***

166 To measure the hydrodynamic diameters (dH) of the particles, micelles and aggregates in the
167 extracts solutions a Zetasizer Nano-ZS (Malvern Instruments Ltd., United Kingdom), working
168 on the basis of a non-invasive backscattering method, was applied. The measurements were

169 carried out at $22 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for solutions of extracts' concentrations: $0.3\times\text{CMC}$, $1.0\times\text{CMC}$, and
170 $3\times\text{CMC}$.

171

172 ***2.6. Statistical analysis***

173

174 All experiments and measurements were conducted in triplicate. For further calculations
175 arithmetic means and standard deviations were used. The calculations were conducted in
176 MATLAB software.

177 **3. Results and discussion**

178 ***3.1. Analysis of the qualitative composition of the *Saponaria officinalis* fraction***

179 The cleaned-up extracts from *Saponaria officinalis* L. were analysed using the LC-MS/MS
180 system. No saponins were detected in extract E3, but they were found in the other two extracts
181 (E1 and E2). Both these clearer extracts showed cleaner spectra than that obtained for the extract
182 not subjected to cleaning (extract E0). However, there was no considerable difference between
183 extracts E1 and E2, both contained the same saponins. The saponins identified in these two
184 extracts are collected in Table 1. The aglycones found in the samples are characteristic of
185 *Saponaria officinalis* L. as described in previous studies, including gypsogenin,
186 hydroxygypsogenic acid, quillaic acid, hederagenin, hydroxyhederagenin, and phytolaccagenic
187 acid, whose characteristic ions were detected at m/z 176, 501, 485, 471, 487, and 515,
188 respectively (Budan et al., 2014; Lu et al., 2015; Moniuszko-Szajwaj et al., 2013; Smulek et
189 al., 2017). From among sugars, mainly hexoses and their uronic acids were detected for which
190 losses of 162 and 176 Da were found. Other characteristic losses were also observed in the mass
191 spectra, i.e. 132 Da (pentose), 44 Da (CO_2 from the carboxylic group), or 18 Da (water). Among
192 the detected saponins, there were two of the most intensive signals: hydroxygypsogenic acid-
193 HexA-Pen-Pen-dHex detected as $[\text{M-H}]^-$ ion at m/z 1087 and quillaic acid- Hex-HexA detected

194 as [M-H]⁻ ion at m/z 823 (Fig. S1) Chromatograms and mass spectra of these compounds are
195 presented in Fig. S2, and their characteristic ions are given in Table 2.

196 The GC-MS analysis performed does not allow a complete analysis of the composition of both
197 fractions of extracts because of the type of detector and the molecular weight of the saponins.
198 However, it enabled an analysis of the sugar components that may be included in the saponin
199 molecules present in the extracted fractions. On the basis of the LC-MS analysis, the
200 compounds with a high signal to noise ratio (S/N) and those present in both fractions were
201 selected. They originated from pentose group: L-(-)-Arabitol and from hexose group: D-(-)-
202 Fructopyranose, α -D-(+)-Mannopyranose, α -D-(-)-Tagatopyranose, D- Psicose, these
203 compounds may be included in the saponins and are labelled as Pen - pentoses or Hex - hexoses,
204 in Table 1. These are only the suggested chemical compounds. The similarities in the structures
205 of the above-mentioned compounds, as well as the fact that the studied systems are plant
206 extracts, make it extremely difficult to find the exact answer to the question of what sugar parts
207 attach to specific aglycone parts. Attention should be paid to the high content of sugar alcohols,
208 which, like saponins, may arise as a result of metabolic changes taking place in plant cells
209 (Bieleski, 1982; Zhang, 1996). These are for example D-(-)-Ribofuranose or D-(-)-
210 Fructofuranose, D-Pinitol, D-Mannitol.

211

212 ***3.2. Surface tension***

213 The shape of the surface tension isotherms of the aqueous solutions of various types of
214 surfactants and the minimum attainable values of the surface tension of these solutions provide
215 information on the adsorption activity of a given compound. The minimum values of the surface
216 tension of the aqueous solutions of extracts E0, E1, E2, E3 and E4 do not differ much from each
217 other and are much higher than the minimum values of aqueous solutions of the classic non-
218 ionic, anionic and cationic surfactants (Figs. 2 and 3) (Zdziennicka et al., 2012a). Since, as

219 mentioned above, individual extract fractions contain many compounds, composed of both
220 small and large molecules, it is difficult to present the changes of the surface tension of the
221 investigated solutions as a function of the molar concentration. Therefore, in order to compare
222 the isotherms of the surface tension of the aqueous solution of extract fractions with the
223 isotherms of the aqueous solutions of the representatives classic surfactants, the isotherms of
224 the extract fraction E0, nonionic Triton X-165 (TX165), anionic sodium dodecyl sulphate
225 (SDS) and cationic hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) as a function of the
226 logarithm of their masses in 1 L are presented in Fig. 2 as an example. The comparison of the
227 surface tension isotherms of aqueous solutions of the synthetic surfactants with those obtained
228 for the solution of saponins may be useful for prediction of the properties of saponins mixtures
229 with the classical surfactants. This seems to be important for the practical application of the
230 saponins.

231 Fig. 2 shows that the shape of the surface tension isotherm of the aqueous solution of extract
232 E0 fraction is similar to that of the nonionic TX165 solution. However, the values of the surface
233 tension of the aqueous E0 solution, at a given concentration, are between those for the cationic
234 CTAB and anionic SDS solutions. Indeed, as mentioned above, the minimum surface tension
235 value of the E0 solution is much higher than that of the TX165, SDS and CTAB solutions. It is
236 worth noting that the concentration corresponding to the critical micelle concentration (CMC)
237 for E0 is similar to the CMC of SDS.

238 A question arises why there are so great differences in the values of the minimum surface
239 tension between the aqueous fractionate solutions and those of classic synthetic surfactants.

240 The surface tension of the aqueous surfactant solutions depends on the surface tension of water
241 and all solution components as well as the contribution of various types of intermolecular
242 interactions to the surface tension of water and surfactants. For the first time, Fowkes (1964)
243 has noted that for a better understanding of interface phenomena, not only the measured surface

244 tension of a liquid or solution and the indirectly determined surface tension of solids are
245 important, but also the contribution of particular types of intermolecular interactions to this
246 tension. Taking this into account, from the practical point of view, the surface tension of liquids
247 and solids can be treated as the sum of the dispersive and non-dispersive components. In turn,
248 van Oss et al. in their studies (van Oss, 1994; van Oss et al., 1987; van Oss and Costanzo, 1992;
249 van Oss and Good, 1989) divided the surface tension of the solid into the Lifshitz-van der Waals
250 (LW) and acid-base (AB) components. The LW component results from dispersion, dipole-
251 dipole and induced dipole-dipole intermolecular interactions. However, they have estimated
252 that the contribution of the dipole-dipole and dipole-induced dipole interactions in the
253 condensed phases to the surface tension is smaller than 2% (van Oss, 1994; van Oss et al., 1987;
254 van Oss and Costanzo, 1992; van Oss and Good, 1989). Thus the LW component in the van
255 Oss et al. approach to the surface tension is equal to the dispersion component in the Fowkes
256 theory (Fowkes, 1964). The acid-base component of the solid and liquid surface tension is
257 practically associated with the hydrogen bonds formation. As a matter of fact, in the van Oss et
258 al. concept, the electrostatic interactions are not taken into account. In turn, van Oss and
259 Costanzo (van Oss and Costanzo, 1992) have reported that the surface tension of surfactants
260 depends on their molecules orientation toward the air phase. If the molecules are oriented with
261 the tail to the air, the surface tension of surfactants is called the tail surfactant surface tension
262 but if the surfactants molecule are oriented with the head to the air, the surfactant surface tension
263 is called the head surface tension.

264 Taking into account the tail surface tensions of TX165, SDS and CTAB and assuming that their
265 molecules in the monolayer at the water-air interface are oriented with the tail toward the air
266 and that the monolayer is saturated, the minimal surface tension of the aqueous solutions of the
267 surfactants should be about 22, 25 and 27 mN m⁻¹ (Rekiel et al., 2022). In practice, the minimal
268 values of the surface tension of TX165, SDS and CTAB aqueous solutions are considerably

269 higher than these values (Zdziennicka et al., 2012a). Moreover, the LW component of surface
270 tension of these surfactant solutions does not depend on the concentration and is close to the
271 LW component of the water surface tension (26.85 mN m⁻¹) (Zdziennicka et al., 2017). This
272 indicates that the addition of the classical synthetic surfactants to water and their adsorption at
273 the water-air interface reduce only the AB component of the water surface tension resulting
274 from the hydrogen bonds interactions.

275 The earlier studies of the sugar surfactants showed that their surface tension at the orientation
276 of these surfactants molecules with the hydrophilic groups toward the air (the so-called the head
277 surface tension) was greater than 40 mN m⁻¹ (Zdziennicka et al., 2018) and was determined by
278 the Lifshitz-van der Waals and hydrogen bonds intermolecular interactions. However, the
279 contribution of the LW component to the sugar head surface tension was significantly greater
280 than that of the AB one. As the compounds present in the given fraction of a extract have
281 different types of sugar units, it should be expected that their surface tension is greater than 40
282 mN m⁻¹ and the contribution of AB component to this tension is considerably smaller than that
283 of the LW one. This is probably the reason for the higher minimal values of the surface tension
284 of particular fractions of the extract than those for the classic synthetic surfactants.

285 In order to be able to analyse the adsorption properties of the studied extract fractions in the
286 whole range of their concentration in the bulk phase, it is important to describe the surface
287 tension isotherms with an appropriate mathematical or thermodynamic equation. It has been
288 proved that the obtained surface tension isotherms can be described by the exponential function
289 of the second order (Fig. 3). This function has the form:

$$290 \quad \gamma_{LV} = \gamma_0 + A_1 \exp\left(\frac{-m}{t_1}\right) +$$
$$291 \quad A_2 \exp\left(\frac{-m}{t_2}\right) \quad (1)$$

292 where γ_{LV} is the surface tension of the aqueous solution of the extract fraction, m is the weight
293 of the extract in g L⁻¹ and γ_0 , A_1 , A_2 , t_1 and t_2 are the constants.

294 Unfortunately, so far it has been difficult to give the exact dependencies of the constants in Eq.
 295 (1) on the physicochemical properties of the solution components. However, it seems likely
 296 that these constants are related to the components and parameters of the surface tension of the
 297 compounds present in the solution. The LW components of this tension can be associated with
 298 γ_0 constant. The values of γ_0 (Table 3) for particular fractions of the extract are insignificantly
 299 lower than the minimal values of their aqueous solution surface tension. On the other hand, the
 300 values of γ_0 are only insignificantly different from those of the sugar surfactants head surface
 301 tension (Zdziennicka et al., 2018). It is possible that the A_1 , A_2 , t_1 and t_2 constants in Eq. (1)
 302 are related to the formation and breaking of hydrogen bonds. In other words, they depend on
 303 the electron-acceptor and electron-donor parameters of the surface tension of surfactants.
 304 Our earlier studies have proved that the surface tension isotherms of the aqueous solutions not
 305 only of individual surfactants but also of their mixtures can be successfully described by the
 306 Szyszkowski equation. For the aqueous solution of individual surfactants this equation takes
 307 the form (Rosen, 2004):

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \gamma_W - \gamma_{LV} \\
 & = RT\Gamma^{max} \ln\left(\frac{C}{a} + 1\right)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

310 where γ_W is the water surface tension, Γ^{max} is the surfactant maximal Gibbs surface excess
 311 concentration at the water-air interface, R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, C
 312 is the surfactant concentration in mole L^{-1} and a is the constant depending on the Gibbs free
 313 energy of adsorption.

314 Eq.(2) has been successfully used for description of the surface tension isotherms of the aqueous
 315 solutions of single surfactants and their mixtures if the concentration of the surfactants and/or
 316 their mixture at which they were present in the solution in the monomeric form was taken into
 317 account in this equation (Rekiel et al., 2022). In the case of the surfactants mixtures at the
 318 constant composition, the sum of the concentrations of the mixture components in the bulk

319 phase and the maximal Gibbs surface excess concentration of the mixture were used for the
320 isotherm surface tension determination from the Szyszkowski equation (Zdziennicka et al.,
321 2012a).

322 For the calculation of the isotherm of the surface tension of particular fractions of the extract,
323 it is impossible to use the Szyszkowski equation in the form of Eq. (2) because we do not know
324 the molar concentration of a given fraction of the extract. However, in Eq. (2) $\frac{m}{M_s}$ can be used
325 instead of C , where $M_s = \sum_{i=j}^{i=1} \alpha_i M_i$ (α_i is the mole fraction of i – th component in the mixture,
326 j is the number of components and M_i is the molar weight of i – th component). In such a case
327 Eq. (2) takes the form:

$$\begin{aligned} 328 \quad & \gamma_w - \gamma_{LV} \\ 329 \quad & = RT\Gamma^{max} \ln \left(\frac{m}{aM_s} + 1 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

330 It proved that using Eq. (3) it is possible to describe the surface tension isotherm of the aqueous
331 solution of all studied fractions of the extract (Fig. 3). In fact, Eq. (3) can be solved against
332 γ_{LV} numerically by fitting the Γ^{max} and aM_s values. The Γ^{max} (Table 3) and aM_s values obtained
333 in such a way depend on the type of the extract fraction.

334 As follows from the surface tension isotherms for the aqueous solution of particular fractions
335 of the extract, the aggregation process may take place. Most probably the CMCs of the extracts
336 E0, E1, E2, E3 and E4 are 1.5, 1.29, 1.5, 2.33 and 1.3 g L⁻¹, respectively. From among these
337 CMC values, the value for E3 is the least certain. For comparison of the CMC values obtained
338 for different fractions of the extract with those of TX165, SDS and CTAB, the CMC values of
339 the latter were calculated in g L⁻¹ to be close to 0.493, 2.365 and 0.334 g L⁻¹, respectively. Thus,
340 the CMC values of the particular extract fractions are smaller only than the CMC value of the
341 anionic SDS (Zdziennicka et al., 2012b).

342 **3.3. Concentration at the water-air interface**

343 The concentration of the surfactants in the monolayer at the water-air interface can be
 344 determined, among others, using the Gibbs isotherm and Frumkin equations (Rosen, 2004).
 345 However, it should be remembered that using the Gibbs isotherm equation the excess
 346 concentration of a given compound in the surface layer relative to its concentration in the bulk
 347 phase is determined. In the case of surfactants at their low concentration in the bulk phase, the
 348 concentration of surfactants in the surface layer is considerable higher than that in the bulk
 349 phase and can be treated as a total concentration.

350 For the multicomponent surfactant mixtures in which the concentration of the surfactants
 351 without one component is constant and the coefficient of the surfactants activity is equal to
 352 unity, the Gibbs isotherm equation takes the form (Rosen, 2004):

$$\begin{aligned}
 353 \quad \Gamma_i &= -\frac{C_i}{RT} \left(\frac{\partial \gamma_{LV}}{\partial C_i} \right)_{C_{j \neq i}, T} \\
 354 \quad &= -\frac{1}{2.303RT} \left(\frac{\partial \gamma_{LV}}{\partial \log C_i} \right)_{C_{j \neq i}, T} \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

355 where Γ_i is the Gibbs surface excess concentration of the i -th component of the mixture, C_i is
 356 the concentration of the i -th component in the bulk phase.

357 In the case of the ionic surfactants, the constant kRT is used in. Eq. (4) instead of RT . Assuming
 358 that the activity of water is equal to unity, then for the aqueous solution of the multicomponent
 359 surfactants mixture at a constant composition and the variable total mixture concentration, the
 360 Gibbs-Duhem equation for the surface region has the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 361 \quad Ad + \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} n_i d \Gamma_i \\
 362 \quad = 0 \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

363 where A is the area of the interface, n_i is the number of moles of the i -th component in the
 364 solution, j is the number of the components in the mixture and μ_i is the chemical potential of
 365 the i -th component in the interface region.

366 In fact, in the equilibrium state, the chemical potential of all components in the surface layer is
 367 equal to their chemical potential in the bulk phase. If the concentration of all components of the
 368 solution in the bulk phase is considerably smaller than the number of water moles in 1 L, it can
 369 be assumed that:

$$370 \quad a_i = X_i = \frac{C\alpha_i}{\omega}$$

$$371 \quad = \frac{m\alpha_i}{M_S\omega} \quad (6)$$

372 where a_i is the activity of the i -th component in the bulk phase, X_i is the mole fraction of the i -
 373 th component in the bulk phase, C is the total concentration of the surfactants mixture in the
 374 bulk phase in mol L⁻¹, m is the weight of the surfactants mixture in g in 1 L of solution, α_i is the
 375 mole fraction of the i -th component in the surfactants mixture in the bulk phase and ω is the
 376 number of the water moles in 1 L.

377 Putting Eq. (6) into Eq. (5) we obtain:

$$378 \quad = -\frac{m}{RT} \left(\frac{\partial \gamma_{LV}}{\partial m} \right)_T = -\frac{1}{2.303RT} \left(\frac{\partial \gamma_{LV}}{\partial \log m} \right)_T \quad (7)$$

379 The values calculated from Eq. (7) depend on the type of the extract fraction (Fig. 4). For the
 380 calculation of Γ from Eq. (7), kRT cannot be used instead of RT because in the studied mixtures
 381 the amount of acid compounds is small. In such a case the values of k should be very close to
 382 unity and are difficult to establish precisely. It is interesting that in some cases the maximal
 383 Gibbs surface excess concentration of the extract fraction calculated based on Eq (7) is
 384 comparable to that deduced from the Szyszkowski equation. The surface tension isotherms of

385 the studied mixtures can be also determined from the Szyszkowski-Langmuir equation, which
386 can be expressed in the following form:

387
$$\gamma - \gamma_{LV} = \pi$$

388
$$= -RT \Gamma^{max} \ln \left(1 - \frac{\Gamma}{\Gamma^{max}} \right) \quad (8)$$

389 where: γ is the water surface tension.

390 However, it should be noted that Eq. (8) is also known as the Frumkin equation (Rosen, 2004).

391 Taking into account the Γ^{max} values obtained from Eq. (7) the Γ values were calculated from
392 Eq. (8) (Fig. 4). It proved that the shape of isotherms obtained from Eq. (8) is different than
393 that of the isotherms determined using Eq. (7). The differences between the Gibbs and Frumkin
394 isotherms of Γ depend on the type of the extract fraction. Taking into account the complexity of
395 the studied systems, it is currently difficult to establish the reasons for these differences.

396 As mentioned above, it is difficult to determine the exact Γ values due to the presence of
397 anionic compounds in the particular fractions of the extract. It can be only concluded
398 that the real values of the surface excess concentration of the investigated fractions of
399 the extract at the water-air interface are in the range from $\Gamma/2$ to Γ . The Γ^{max} values
400 obtained for the extract fractions E0, E2 and E3 are comparable to those for the
401 saponins. It probably results from the fact that these fractions contain the compounds
402 whose adsorption properties are close to those of saponins. Unfortunately, it is difficult
403 to establish which compounds have the same adsorption properties as saponins. On
404 the other hand, the Γ^{max} values for the fractions E0, E2 and E3 are insignificantly
405 smaller than the value of Γ^{max} for TX165 (Zdziennicka et al., 2012b). However, the
406 Γ^{max} value for E1 is insignificantly smaller than the maximal values of the Gibbs surface
407 excess concentration of ionic SDS and CTAB. The smallest value of Γ^{max} was obtained
408 for E4 (Table 3).

409 On the basis of the max value it is possible to determine the minimal average value
410 of the area occupied by one molecule of a given extract fraction (A_{min}) in the monolayer
411 at the water-air interface using the simple expression:

$$412 \quad A_{min}$$
$$413 \quad = \frac{1}{^{max}N} \quad (9)$$

414 where: N is the Avogadro number.

415 It appeared that the calculated values of A_{min} for all extract fractions are higher than the
416 contactable area of sugar units (Zdziennicka et al., 2018). However, it is very difficult to
417 establish the orientation of the compound molecules present in a given extract fraction in the
418 mixed monolayer at the water-air interface based on this comparison.

419

420 ***3.4. Standard Gibbs free energy of adsorption and micellization***

421 The standard Gibbs free energy of adsorption (G_{ads}^0) and micellization (G_{mic}^0) are the measures
422 of the tendency of the surfactants to get adsorbed at the interfaces and to form the colloidal
423 aggregates in the bulk phase, called micelles. A number of methods have been reported for
424 determination of ΔG_{ads}^0 and G_{mic}^0 . If we have the isotherm of the surfactants Gibbs surface
425 excess concentration at the water-air interface in their concentration range in the bulk phase
426 from zero to a concentration even higher than CMC, the standard Gibbs surface free energy of
427 adsorption can be determined using the Langmuir equation modified by de Boer (de Boer,
428 1953; Rosen, 2004). This equation has the form (Rosen, 2004):

$$429 \quad \frac{A^0}{A - A^0} \exp \frac{A^0}{A - A^0}$$
$$430 \quad = \frac{C}{\omega} \exp \left(\frac{-\Delta G_{ads}^0}{RT} \right) \quad (10)$$

431 where A^0 is the limiting area occupied by one surfactant molecule and A is the area occupied
432 by one surfactant molecule in the monolayer at the interface corresponding to a given mole
433 concentration C , respectively.

434 To solve Eq. (10) the knowledge of A^0 , A and C is needed. As a matter of fact, A can be
435 calculated from Eq. (9) which applies not only for A_{min} determination. However, to establish
436 the A^0 value for the particular fraction of the extract, which is the multicomponent mixture,
437 none of the known concepts can be used. Taking into account the composition of the particular
438 fraction of the extract, it seems reasonable that the A^0 value should be close to the contactable
439 area of the sugar unit (35 \AA^2) (Zdziennicka et al., 2018). This results from the fact that the
440 molecules of the most compounds present in the extract fraction contain the groups whose size
441 is close to that of the sugar unit. In the case of diluted solutions, the value of A^0 has an
442 insignificant impact on the ΔG_{ads}^0 value calculated from Eq. (10). Another problem to solve Eq.
443 (10) against ΔG_{ads}^0 is to establish the C value of the extract fraction. As two membranes with
444 the porosity of 500 and 3000 Da were used in the fractionation process of the extract, the
445 molecular weight was assumed to be equal to 500 and 3000 g, respectively for the C
446 calculations.

447 Using the A^0 and C values determined in the above mentioned ways and the A values
448 determined based on the Gibbs isotherm of the excess concentration of particular extract
449 fraction in Eq. (10), two ΔG_{ads}^0 values were calculated for E0, E1, E2, E3 and E4 (Table 3) (Fig.
450 5). It proved that the absolute values of ΔG_{ads}^0 for all types of extract fractions are smaller than
451 that for TX165, SDS and CTAB (Table 3) (Zdziennicka et al., 2012a). These values of ΔG_{ads}^0
452 depend on the type of the extract fraction.

453 Of course, the question arises whether the values of molecular weight used for the calculation
454 of the standard Gibbs free energy of adsorption give its reasonable values for the particular

455 components of the extract fraction. According to the experimental procedure, the maximal
456 molecular weight of the compounds cannot be higher than 3000 g. However, the minimal
457 molecular weight is not equal to 500 g. On the other hand, the molecular weight of more than
458 90% compounds present in the studied solutions is higher than 250 g. If in the calculation of
459 ΔG_{ads}^0 the compounds of molecular weight of 250 g are used instead of those of 500 g, then the
460 obtained values differed by less than 2 kJ mol⁻¹. Thus, for all fractions from the *Saponaria*
461 extract, the calculations of ΔG_{ads}^0 were made assuming that the molecular weight of compounds
462 was equal to 500 or 3000 g which corresponds numerically to the porosity of the membranes.
463 It seems to be interesting to calculate the ΔG_{ads}^0 values based on the constant established solving
464 the Szyszkowski equation against the surface tension of the aqueous solution of extract
465 fractions.

466 Dividing aM_s by 500 or 3000, two values of a were obtained for each fraction of the extract
467 and then the G_{ads}^0 values were calculated from the following equation (Rosen, 2004):

468
$$a$$

469
$$= \omega \exp \frac{\Delta G_{ads}^0}{RT} \quad (11)$$

470 In many cases, the values of ΔG_{ads}^0 calculated from Eq. (11) are close to those obtained from
471 Eq. (10). This indicates that using the Szyszkowski equation both the maximal Gibbs surface
472 excess concentration as well as the standard Gibbs free energy of adsorption of such
473 complicated systems can be determined. In fact, the ΔG_{ads}^0 values calculated from Eq. (11) are
474 higher than that for TX165 and smaller than those for SDS and CTAB (Zdziennicka et al.,
475 2012a) (Table 3).

476 According to Zdziennicka and Jańczuk (Zdziennicka and Jańczuk, 2017) the G_{ads}^0 values are
477 correlated with the standard Gibbs free energy of micellization (ΔG_{mic}^0) by the following
478 expression:

$$479 \quad G_{ads}^0$$
$$480 \quad = RT \ln \frac{CMC}{\Gamma_{LV}^{min}} - \frac{W_{LV}^{min}}{\Gamma_{LV}^{max}} \quad (12)$$

481 where $RT \ln \frac{CMC}{\Gamma_{LV}^{min}}$ is equal to ΔG_{mic}^0 .

482 For the calculations of G_{ads}^0 from this equation, the values of Γ^{max} determined from Eq. (7) and
483 γ_{LV}^{min} as well as CMC obtained based on the surface tension isotherms (Figs. 2 and 3) were taken
484 into account. The values of ΔG_{ads}^0 calculated from Eq. (12) are slightly smaller than those
485 calculated from Eqs. (10) and (11). However, they are higher than ΔG_{ads}^0 values for TX165 and
486 smaller than those for SDS and CTAB. (Table 3) (Zdziennicka et al., 2012a).

487 In turn, the ΔG_{mic}^0 calculated from Eq. (12) is comparable to that of TX165, being smaller than
488 the values for SDS and CTAB, and depends on the type of the extract fraction (Table 3)
489 (Zdziennicka et al., 2012a).

490

491 **3.5. Particle size distribution**

492 The final stage of the research was the determination of micelle size of particular extract
493 fractions. The particle size distribution analysis was performed using the previously obtained
494 information on the CMC of individual fractions, to provide additional information about the
495 hydrodynamic diameter of micelles, depending on the concentration. Tests were carried out
496 using a concentration three times lower than CMC - $0.3 \times CMC$, at CMC - $1.0 \times CMC$, and three
497 times higher than CMC - $3.0 \times CMC$. The results are shown in Fig. 6. For each fraction the
498 particle size calculated for the concentrations of $1.0 \times CMC$ and $3.0 \times CMC$ were the same. For

499 the fractions E0, E3 and E4 the particles' hydrodynamic diameters for the concentration of
500 $1.0\times\text{CMC}$ and $3.0\times\text{CMC}$ differed from that calculated for $0.3\times\text{CMC}$. However, there is a
501 significant difference in the micelle size distribution between the E0 fraction - crude extract,
502 and the fractions obtained after nanofiltration. As mentioned above, an extract is a mixture of
503 many compounds, ranging from proteins, through lipids and waxes, to sugars. The E0 fraction
504 is the crude extract and thus differences may arise. It is, therefore, worth noting that depending
505 on the degree of purification of the extract and its concentration, the hydrodynamic diameter of
506 particles is different. For the fractions E1 and E4, the size of the micelles ranges from approx.
507 37 nm to 120 nm, and for E2 from 24 nm to 105 nm. According to Milovanovic et al. (2017),
508 these values corresponded to typical micelle size range from 5 to 100 nm. On the other hand,
509 the volume fractions signals appearing on each spectra between 220 nm and 1000 nm may
510 correspond to the aggregated forms of micelles. As observed by Samal et al. (2017),
511 agglomerates of *Sapindus mukorossi* saponin micelles were also present in aqueous solution
512 having particle size ranging from 132-235 nm, 390-990 nm, and 5155-8520 nm, which
513 corresponds to the value obtained in our research. It is worth noting the lack of such signals for
514 the fraction E3. In the case of the crude extract, the percentage of particles with a size from 37
515 nm to 91 nm is very limited. Particles with a size from 2300 nm to 5560 nm have the largest
516 share, which suggests almost no disaggregated micelles.

517

518 **4. Conclusions**

519 Based on the carried out experiments and the analysis of the obtained results many conclusions
520 can be drawn. The chromatographic-mass spectrometry analysis indicated the presence of
521 saponins, the derivatives of gypsogenin, hydroxygypsogenic acid, quillaic acid, hederagenin,
522 hydroxyhederagenin, and phytolaccagenic acid in the *S. officinalis* extract and showed great
523 enrichment in their content in the fraction between 500 Da and 3000 Da.

524 The surface tension isotherms of the aqueous solution of different extracts' fractions can be
525 described by the exponential function of the second order and the constants of this function are
526 related to the components and parameters of the compounds present in the extract fraction.

527 It was observed that the saponins have non-ionic nature which is in accordance with the
528 suggestions following from other research works.

529 The standard Gibbs free energy of micellization indicates that plant extracts have the greater
530 tendency to aggregate than the classical synthetic surfactants. The thermodynamic equations
531 used for the determination of Gibbs surface excess concentration isotherms as well as the
532 standard Gibbs free energy of adsorption and micellization for the aqueous solution of
533 individual surfactants and their mixtures can be customized to so complicated solution as the
534 aqueous solution of fraction of extract. What is more, the saponin-rich fraction of the extract
535 formed nanometric micelles and agglomerates, which were of smaller size than those formed
536 in the other extract fractions.

537 The presented analyses constitute an appropriate basis for further planned research, as they
538 confirm the effectiveness of extract purification, present the qualitative analysis as well as the
539 CMC values that will support the application of bioactive *S. officinalis* extract in
540 pharmaceutical, cosmetic and food products.

541

542 **Acknowledgements**

543 This research was funded in whole by National Science Centre, Poland, grant number:
544 2020/39/B/NZ9/03196.

545

546 **Conflicts of Interest**

547 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

548

549 **Ethical approval**

550 This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by any
551 of the authors.

552 **Data Availability Statement**

553 The raw/processed data are available after e-mail contact with the corresponding author.

554

555 **References**

556 Benhur, A.M., Pingali, S., Amin, S., 2020. Application of Biosurfactants and Biopolymers in
557 Sustainable Cosmetic Formulation Design. *J Cosmet Sci* 71, 455–480.

558 Bieleski, R.L., 1982. Sugar Alcohols, in: Loewus, F.A., Tanner, W. (Eds.), *Plant Carbohydrates*
559 I. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 158–192.
560 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-68275-9_5

561 Bjerck, T.R., Severino, P., Jain, S., Marques, C., Silva, A.M., Pashirova, T., Souto, E.B., 2021.
562 Biosurfactants: Properties and Applications in Drug Delivery, Biotechnology and
563 Ecotoxicology. *Bioengineering* 8, 115. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bioengineering8080115>

564 Budan, A., Bellenot, D., Freuze, I., Gillmann, L., Chicoteau, P., Richomme, P., Guilet, D.,
565 2014. Potential of extracts from *Saponaria officinalis* and *Calendula officinalis* to
566 modulate *in vitro* rumen fermentation with respect to their content in saponins.
567 *Bioscience, Biotechnology, and Biochemistry* 78, 288–295.
568 <https://doi.org/10.1080/09168451.2014.882742>

569 De Boer, H., 1953. *The Dynamical Character of Adsorption*. Oxford University, Oxford, UK.

570 Fowkes, F.M., 1964. ATTRACTIVE FORCES AT INTERFACES. *Ind. Eng. Chem.* 56, 40–52.
571 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie50660a008>

572 Fujimatu, E., Ishikawa, T., Kitajima, J., 2003. Aromatic compound glucosides, alkyl glucoside
573 and glucide from the fruit of anise. *Phytochemistry* 63, 609–616.
574 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-9422\(03\)00179-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-9422(03)00179-1)

575 Hussain, M., Debnath, B., Qasim, M., Bamisile, B.S., Islam, W., Hameed, M.S., Wang, L., Qiu,
576 D., 2019. Role of Saponins in Plant Defense Against Specialist Herbivores. *Molecules*
577 24, 2067. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24112067>

578 Jung, M.-H., Jung, S.-J., Kim, T., 2022. Saponin and chitosan-based oral vaccine against viral
579 haemorrhagic septicaemia virus (VHSV) provides protective immunity in olive flounder
580 (*Paralichthys olivaceus*). *Fish & Shellfish Immunology* 126, 336–346.
581 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsi.2022.05.044>

582 Karlapudi, A.P., Venkateswarulu, T.C., Tammineedi, J., Kanumuri, L., Ravuru, B.K., Dirisala,
583 V. ramu, Kodali, V.P., 2018. Role of biosurfactants in bioremediation of oil pollution-
584 a review. *Petroleum* 4, 241–249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petlm.2018.03.007>

585 Kobayashi, T., Kaminaga, H., Navarro, R.R., Iimura, Y., 2012. Application of aqueous saponin
586 on the remediation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons-contaminated soil. *Journal of*
587 *Environmental Science and Health, Part A* 47, 1138–1145.
588 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10934529.2012.668106>

589 Korchowicz, B., Gorczyca, M., Wojszko, K., Janikowska, M., Henry, M., Rogalska, E., 2015.
590 Impact of two different saponins on the organization of model lipid membranes.
591 *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Biomembranes* 1848, 1963–1973.
592 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbamem.2015.06.007>

593 Lu, Y., Van, D., Deibert, L., Bishop, G., Balsevich, J., 2015. Antiproliferative quillaic acid and
594 gypsogenin saponins from *Saponaria officinalis* L. roots. *Phytochemistry* 113, 108–120.
595 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2014.11.021>

596 Man, S., Gao, W., Zhang, Y., Huang, L., Liu, C., 2010. Chemical study and medical application
597 of saponins as anti-cancer agents. *Fitoterapia* 81, 703–714.
598 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fitote.2010.06.004>

599 Milovanovic, M., Arsenijevic, A., Milovanovic, J., Kanjevac, T., Arsenijevic, N., 2017.
600 Nanoparticles in Antiviral Therapy, in: *Antimicrobial Nanoarchitectonics*. Elsevier, pp.
601 383–410. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-52733-0.00014-8>

602 Moniuszko-Szajwaj, B., Pecio, Ł., Kowalczyk, M., Simonet, A.M., Macias, F.A., Szumacher-
603 Strabel, M., Cieślak, A., Oleszek, W., Stochmal, A., 2013. New Triterpenoid Saponins
604 from the Roots of *Saponaria officinalis*. *Natural Product Communications* 8,
605 1934578X1300801. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1934578X1300801207>

606 Nizioł-Lukaszewska, Z., Bujak, T., 2018. Saponins as Natural Raw Materials for Increasing
607 the Safety of Bodywash Cosmetic Use. *J Surfactants Deterg* 21, 767–776.
608 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsde.12168>

609 Pradhan, A., Bhuyan, S., Chhetri, K., Mandal, S., Bhattacharyya, A., 2022. Saponins from
610 *Albizia procera* extract: Surfactant activity and preliminary analysis. *Colloids and*
611 *Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* 643, 128778.
612 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2022.128778>

613 Randriamamonjy, T.H., Ontiveros, J.F., Andrianjafy, M.T., Samiez, P., Berlioz-Barbier, A.,
614 Nardello-Rataj, V., Aubry, J.-M., Ramanandraibe, V., Lemaire, M., 2022. Comparative
615 study on the amphiphilicity, emulsifying and foaming properties of saponins extracted
616 from *Furcraea foetida*. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering*
617 *Aspects* 653, 129923. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2022.129923>

618 Rekiel, E., Smulek, W., Zdziennicka, A., Kaczorek, E., Jańczuk, B., 2020. Wetting properties
619 of *Saponaria officinalis* saponins. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and*
620 *Engineering Aspects* 584, 123980. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2019.123980>

621 Rekiel, E., Zdziennicka, A., Szymczyk, K., Jańczuk, B., 2022. Thermodynamic Analysis of the
622 Adsorption and Micellization Activity of the Mixtures of Rhamnolipid and Surfactin
623 with Triton X-165. *Molecules* 27, 3600. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27113600>

624 Rodrigues, L., Banat, I.M., Teixeira, J., Oliveira, R., 2006. Biosurfactants: potential
625 applications in medicine. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy* 57, 609–618.
626 <https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkl024>

627 Rosen, M.J., 2004. *Surfactants and interfacial phenomena*, 3rd ed. ed. Wiley-Interscience,
628 Hoboken, N.J.

629 Samal, K., Das, C., Mohanty, K., 2017. Eco-friendly biosurfactant saponin for the solubilization
630 of cationic and anionic dyes in aqueous system. *Dyes and Pigments* 140, 100–108.
631 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dyepig.2017.01.031>

632 Schreiner, T.B., Colucci, G., Santamaria-Echart, A., Fernandes, I.P., Dias, M.M., Pinho, S.P.,
633 Barreiro, M.F., 2021. Evaluation of saponin-rich extracts as natural alternative
634 emulsifiers: A comparative study with pure Quillaja Bark saponin. *Colloids and*
635 *Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* 623, 126748.
636 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2021.126748>

637 Servillo, L., Giovane, A., Balestrieri, M.L., Bata-Csere, A., Cautela, D., Castaldo, D., 2011.
638 Betaines in Fruits of *Citrus* Genus Plants. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 59, 9410–9416.
639 <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf2014815>

640 Smulek, W., Rojewska, M., Pacholak, A., Machrowicz, O., Prochaska, K., Kaczorek, E., 2022.
641 Co-interaction of nitrofurantoin and saponins surfactants with biomembrane leads to an
642 increase in antibiotic's antibacterial activity. *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 364, 120070.
643 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2022.120070>

644 Smulek, W., Zdarta, A., Pacholak, A., Zgoła-Grześkowiak, A., Marczak, Ł., Jarzębski, M.,
645 Kaczorek, E., 2017. *Saponaria officinalis* L. extract: Surface active properties and

646 impact on environmental bacterial strains. *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces* 150,
647 209–215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfb.2016.11.035>

648 Stanimirova, R., Marinova, K., Tcholakova, S., Denkov, N.D., Stoyanov, S., Pelan, E., 2011.
649 Surface Rheology of Saponin Adsorption Layers. *Langmuir* 27, 12486–12498.
650 <https://doi.org/10.1021/la202860u>

651 Tamura, Y., Miyakoshi, M., Yamamoto, M., 2012. Application of Saponin-Containing Plants
652 in Foods and Cosmetics, in: Sakagami, H. (Ed.), *Alternative Medicine*. InTech.
653 <https://doi.org/10.5772/53333>

654 Tucker, I.M., Burley, A., Petkova, R.E., Hosking, S.L., Webster, J.P., Li, P.X., Ma, K., Douth,
655 J., Penfold, J., Thomas, R.K., 2022. Self-assembly of Quillaja saponin mixtures with
656 different conventional synthetic surfactants. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical
657 and Engineering Aspects* 633, 127854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2021.127854>

658 Van Oss, C.J., 1994. *Interfacial forces in aqueous media*. M. Dekker, New York.

659 van Oss, C.J., Chaudhury, M.K., Good, R.J., 1987. Monopolar surfaces. *Advances in Colloid
660 and Interface Science* 28, 35–64. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-8686\(87\)80008-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-8686(87)80008-8)

661 Van Oss, C.J., Costanzo, P.M., 1992. Adhesion of anionic surfactants to polymer surfaces and
662 low-energy materials. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology* 6, 477–487.
663 <https://doi.org/10.1163/156856192X00809>

664 van Oss, C.J., Good, R.J., 1989. Surface Tension and the Solubility of Polymers and
665 Biopolymers: The Role of Polar and Apolar Interfacial Free Energies. *Journal of
666 Macromolecular Science: Part A - Chemistry* 26, 1183–1203.
667 <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222338908052041>

668 Vincken, J.-P., Heng, L., de Groot, A., Gruppen, H., 2007. Saponins, classification and
669 occurrence in the plant kingdom. *Phytochemistry* 68, 275–297.
670 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2006.10.008>

671 Zdziennicka, A., Jańczuk, B., 2017. Thermodynamic parameters of some biosurfactants and
672 surfactants adsorption at water-air interface. *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 243,
673 236–244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2017.08.042>

674 Zdziennicka, A., Krawczyk, J., Szymczyk, K., Jańczuk, B., 2018. Macroscopic and
675 Microscopic Properties of Some Surfactants and Biosurfactants. *IJMS* 19, 1934.
676 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms19071934>

677 Zdziennicka, A., Szymczyk, K., Krawczyk, J., Jańczuk, B., 2017. Components and parameters
678 of solid/surfactant layer surface tension. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and*
679 *Engineering Aspects* 522, 461–469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2017.03.036>

680 Zdziennicka, A., Szymczyk, K., Krawczyk, J., Jańczuk, B., 2012a. Activity and thermodynamic
681 parameters of some surfactants adsorption at the water–air interface. *Fluid Phase*
682 *Equilibria* 318, 25–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fluid.2012.01.014>

683 Zdziennicka, A., Szymczyk, K., Krawczyk, J., Jańczuk, B., 2012b. Critical micelle
684 concentration of some surfactants and thermodynamic parameters of their micellization.
685 *Fluid Phase Equilibria* 322–323, 126–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fluid.2012.03.018>

686 Zhang, Y., 1996. Enhancement of ginseng saponin production in suspension cultures of *Panax*
687 *notoginseng*: manipulation of medium sucrose. *Journal of Biotechnology* 51, 49–56.
688 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1656\(96\)01560-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1656(96)01560-X)

689

690

691 **Figure captions**

692

693 **Fig. 1.** A scheme of isolation and membrane separation of *Saponaria officinalis* extracts used in
694 the study.

695 **Fig. 2.** A plot of the surface tension (γ_{LV}) of aqueous solutions of the E0 fraction (curve 1),
696 TX165 (curve 2), SDS (curve 3) and CTAB (curve 4) vs. the logarithm of their molecular
697 weight (m) (m – the numerical value corresponding to the weight in g L⁻¹).

698 **Fig. 3.** A plot of the surface tension (γ_{LV}) of aqueous solutions of the fractions E0 (A), E1 (B),
699 E2 (C), E3 (D), E4 (E) vs. the logarithm of their molecular weight (m) (m – the numerical
700 value corresponding to the weight in g L⁻¹). Points 1 correspond to the measured values,
701 curves 2 and 3 correspond to the values calculated from Eqs. (1) and (2), respectively.

702 **Fig. 4.** The plot of the surface excess concentration (Γ) for the fractions E0 (curves 1, 1'), E1
703 (curves 2, 2'), E2 (curves 3, 3'), E3 (curves 4, 4') and E4 (curves 5, 5') vs. the logarithm
704 of their weight (m) (m – the numerical value corresponding to the weight in g L⁻¹). Curves
705 1 – 5 correspond to the values calculated from Eq. (7), curves 1' – 5' to those calculated
706 from Eq. (8).

707 **Fig. 5.** The plot of the standard Gibbs free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}^0) for the fractions E0
708 (curves 1, 1'), E1 (curves 2, 2'), E2 (curves 3, 3'), E3 (curves 4, 4') and E4 (curves 5, 5')
709 calculated from Eq. (10) vs. the logarithm of their molar concentration (C). Curves 1 – 5
710 correspond to the molar concentration calculated for the molecular weight equal to 500
711 g and curves 1' – 5' to molecular weight equal to 3000 g, respectively.

712 **Fig. 6.** Particle size distribution of the individual fractions of the *Saponaria officinalis* extracts
713 (x_v – volume fraction in %, d – hydrodynamic diameter in nm).

A)

D)

B)

E)

C)

Table 1. Structures of saponins found in the *Saponaria officinalis* L. extract.

Aglycone	Sugar units	Mass fragments, m/z	Retention time (s)
Gypsogenin	Hex-HexA	807 [M-H] ⁻ , 645 [M-H-162] ⁻ , 601 [M-H-162-44] ⁻ , 583 [M-H-162-44-18] ⁻ , 469 [M-H-162-176] ⁻ , 451 [M-H-162-176-18] ⁻	12.70
Gypsogenin	HexA	645 [M-H] ⁻ , 469 [M-H-176] ⁻	13.75
Hydroxygypsogenic acid	HexA-Pen-Pen-dHex	1087 [M-H] ⁻ , 911 [M-H-176] ⁻ , 677 [M-H-410] ⁻ , 501 [M-H-176-410] ⁻	12.77
Hydroxygypsogenic acid	Hex-HexA	839 [M-H] ⁻ , 677 [M-H-162] ⁻ , 501 [M-H-162-176] ⁻	12.56
Hydroxygypsogenic acid	Hex	663 [M-H] ⁻ , 501 [M-H-162] ⁻ , 483 [M-H-162-18] ⁻	13.10
Quillaic acid	Hex-HexA	823 [M-H] ⁻ , 661 [M-H-162] ⁻ , 617 [M-H-162-44] ⁻ , 599 [M-H-162-44-18] ⁻ , 485 [M-H-162-176] ⁻ , 467 [M-H-162-176-18] ⁻	12.89
Quillaic acid	HexA	661 [M-H] ⁻ , 485 [M-H-176] ⁻	13.27
Quillaic acid	HexA	661 [M-H] ⁻ , 485 [M-H-176] ⁻ , 467 [M-H-176-18] ⁻	13.78
Hederagenin	Hex-HexA	809 [M-H] ⁻ , 647 [M-H-162] ⁻ , 603 [M-H-162-44] ⁻ , 585 [M-H-162-44-18] ⁻ , 471 [M-H-162-176] ⁻	13.04
Hederagenin	Pen-HexA	779 [M-H] ⁻ , 647 [M-H-132] ⁻ , 471 [M-H-132-176] ⁻	13.18
Hederagenin	HexA	647 [M-H] ⁻ , 471 [M-H-176] ⁻	13.34
Hederagenin	HexA	647 [M-H] ⁻ , 471 [M-H-176] ⁻ , 453 [M-H-176-18] ⁻	14.06
Hydroxyhederagenin	Hex-HexA	825 [M-H] ⁻ , 663 [M-H-162] ⁻ , 619 [M-H-162-44] ⁻ , 601 [M-H-162-44-18] ⁻ , 487 [M-H-162-176] ⁻	12.75
Hydroxyhederagenin	HexA	663 [M-H] ⁻ , 487 [M-H-176] ⁻	13.50
Hydroxyhederagenin	HexA	663 [M-H] ⁻ , 487 [M-H-176] ⁻ , 469 [M-H-176-18] ⁻	13.83
Phytolaccagenic acid	HexA	691 [M-H] ⁻ , 515 [M-H-176] ⁻	13.44
Phytolaccagenic acid	HexA	691 [M-H] ⁻ , 515 [M-H-176] ⁻	13.61

Table 2. Carbohydrates and their derivatives found in the *Saponaria officinalis* L. extract.

Name	R.T. (s)	S/N	Sample
Allyl(methoxy)dimethylsilane	361.9	2564.4	E0
Allyl(methoxy)dimethylsilane	361.9	6138.8	E2
(Z)-Hex-3-enyl (E)-2-methylbut-2-enoate	374.3	1000.1	E2
4-Dimethylsilyloxytridecane	378.6	3241.9	E0
4-Dimethylsilyloxytridecane	378.6	6421.2	E2
Glycerol, tris(trimethylsilyl) ether	741.6	1619.4	E2
Glycerol, tris(trimethylsilyl) ether	742.8	4126.5	E0
meso-Erythritol, tetrakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1040.7	600.13	E0
1,5-Anhydro-D-sorbitol, tetrakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1270.8	731.79	E0
L-(-)-Arabitol, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1281.1	1152	E2
L-(-)-Arabitol, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1281.4	1848.3	E0
Dihydroxyacetone dimer, tetra(trimethylsilyl)-	1318.5	512.41	E2
D-(-)-Tagatofuranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether (isomer 2)	1344.7	691.72	E0
D-(-)-Ribofuranose, tetrakis(trimethylsilyl) ether (isomer 1)	1347.4	924.23	E2
D-(-)-Fructofuranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether (isomer 1)	1373.3	1510.3	E0
D-(-)-Tagatofuranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether (isomer 1)	1381.2	5077.3	E2
D-(-)-Fructofuranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether (isomer 1)	1382.2	2052.9	E0
2,2,4,4,6,6-Hexamethylcyclotrisilazane	1384.4	1787	E0
α -D-(-)-Tagatopyranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1392.5	4217	E2
Ribitol, 1,2,3,4,5-pentakis-O-(trimethylsilyl)-	1397.2	534.25	E2
D-(+)-Talofuranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether (isomer 2)	1417.5	770.57	E2
α -D-(-)-Tagatopyranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1420.9	518.86	E2
D-(-)-Fructofuranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether (isomer 1)	1428.3	1650.3	E2
D-Pinitol, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1431.3	787.34	E0
D-Pinitol, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1433.6	784.17	E2
D-(-)-Fructopyranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether (isomer 2)	1443.4	501.17	E2
α -D-(-)-Tagatopyranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1453.8	18,522	E0
α -D-(+)-Mannopyranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1465.1	614.52	E0
D-Psicose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1469.6	4333.3	E2
D-(+)-Galactopyranose, pentakis(trimethylsilyl) ether (isomer 2)	1474.3	4952.9	E2
Acrylic acid, 2,3-bis[(trimethylsilyloxy)-], trimethylsilyl ester	1480.1	933.97	E2
D-Mannitol, 1,2,3,4,5,6-hexakis-O-(trimethylsilyl)-	1492.4	725.18	E0
D-Mannitol, 1,2,3,4,5,6-hexakis-O-(trimethylsilyl)-	1495.3	2072.7	E2
D-Mannitol, 1,2,3,4,5,6-hexakis-O-(trimethylsilyl)-	1499.2	733	E0
D-Sorbitol. hexakis(trimethylsilyl) ether	1500.8	612.83	E2
α -D-Glucopyranose, 1,2,3,4,6-pentakis-O-(trimethylsilyl)-	1555	696.77	E0
D-Gluconic acid, 2,3,4,5,6-pentakis-O-(trimethylsilyl)-, trimethylsilyl ester	1569.5	729.61	E2

Table 3. The values of the constants in Eq. (1) (y_0 , A_1 , A_2 , t_1 and t_2), maximal Gibbs surface excess concentration (γ^{max}), minimal area occupied by one molecule (A_{min}), critical micelle concentration (CMC) as well as the standard Gibbs free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}^0) and micellization (G_{mic}^0).

Magnitude		E0	E1	E2	E3	E4
Constant in Eq. (1)	y_0	48.03047	44.96415	47.73447	44.51936	48.36917
	A_1	15.17956	6.63508	15.46142	17.6059	10.27968
	t_1	0.52856	0.13625	0.55549	1.84268	0.35042
	A_2	8.33042	20.39518	9.01503	9.1269	9.11056
	t_2	0.04599	1.25044	0.0448	0.07721	0.0494
γ^{max} ($\times 10^{-6}$ mol m $^{-2}$)	Eq. (7)	2.01	2.70	2.00	1.92	1.76
	Eq. (3)	2.20	3.00	2.10	2.00	2.00
aM_s		0.0143	0.0865	0.0134	0.0179	0.0051
A_{min} (\AA^2) Eq. (9)	γ^{max} from Eq. (7)	82.6	61.5	83.0	86.5	94.4
	γ^{max} from Eq. (3)	75.5	55.3	79.1	83.0	83.0
ΔG_{ads}^0 (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	Eq. (10)	-32.55 ^c	-30.91 ^c	-32.86 ^c	-31.32 ^c	-32.58 ^c
		-36.80 ^d	-35.61 ^d	-37.23 ^d	-35.63 ^d	-36.94 ^d
	Eq. (11)	-35.27 ^c	-30.88 ^c	-35.43 ^c	-34.72 ^c	-37.78 ^c
		-39.63 ^d	-35.25 ^d	-39.79 ^d	-39.08 ^d	-42.14 ^d
minimal ΔG_{ads}^0 (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	Eq. (10)	-32.70 ^c	-33.95 ^c	-33.03 ^c	-31.68 ^c	-32.86 ^c
		-37.06 ^d	-38.32 ^d	-37.44 ^d	-36.05 ^d	-37.22 ^d
ΔG_{ads}^0 (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	Eq. (12)	-35.31 ^c	-33.85 ^c	-35.37 ^c	-35.80 ^c	-38.18 ^c
		-39.68 ^d	-38.21 ^d	-39.74 ^d	-40.16 ^d	-42.54 ^d
CMC (g L $^{-1}$)		1.50	1.29	1.50	2.33	1.30
G_{mic}^0 (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	Eq. (12)	-23.92 ^c	-24.29 ^c	-23.92 ^c	-22.85 ^c	-24.27 ^c
		-28.29 ^d	-28.65 ^d	-28.29 ^d	-27.21 ^d	-28.63 ^d

^c – corresponds to the calculation made for the molecular weight $M_s = 500$ g

^d – corresponds to the calculation made for the molecular weight $M_s = 3000$ g

Nanofiltered saponin-rich extract of *Saponaria officinalis* – adsorption and aggregation properties of particular fractions

Conclusions

Nanofiltration is an effective method in saponins purification

Fractions have smaller tendency to adsorb at the water-air interface but bigger to aggregate than the classical synthetic surfactants

Saponins from *Saponaria officinalis* tend to form micelles agglomerates

Supplementary Information

Nanofiltered saponin-rich extract of *Saponaria officinalis* – adsorption and aggregation properties of particular fractions

Submitted to

Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects

by

Adam Grzywaczyk^a, Wojciech Smułek^a, Agnieszka Zgoła-Grześkowiak^b, Ewa Kaczorek^{a*},
Anna Zdziennicka^c and Bronisław Jańczuk^c

^a*Institute of Chemical Technology and Engineering, Poznań University of Technology, Berdychowo 4, 60-965 Poznań, Poland*

^b*Institute of Chemistry and Technical Electrochemistry, Poznań University of Technology, Berdychowo 4, 60-965 Poznań, Poland*

^c*Department of Interfacial Phenomena, Institute of Chemical Sciences, Faculty of Chemistry, Maria Curie-Skłodowska University in Lublin, Maria Curie-Skłodowska Sq. 3, 20-031 Lublin, Poland*

*Corresponding author:

e-mail: ewa.kaczorek@put.poznan.pl, tel. +48 (61) 6652601

Fig S1. Mass spectra of purified (E2) fraction of *Saponaria officinalis*

Fig. S2 Chromatograms (A,C) and mass spectra (B,D) of hydroxygypsogenic acid- HexA-Pen-Pen-dHex (A,B) and quillaic acid- Hex-HexA (C,D).